

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF REALISTIC PAINTING

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Abstract. According to the state educational standard, by studying the rules of drawing from life in a realistic direction, students will understand the content of the realistic direction, as well as the factors and reasons for its emergence in the historical process of fine art, and also being realistic, they must have a specific understanding of the goals and objectives of art. There are certain rules of realistic painting and students must learn them with a clear understanding. Otherwise, students will not be able to understand the essence of realistic painting without highlighting the main aspects of classicism and romanticism, academicism and naturalism. This article provides an analysis of the various aspects of classicism, naturalism, academicism, romanticism and impressionism in the historical process of fine art and the main goal and task of realism in relation to them, as well as options for solving the problem situation.

Keywords: classicism, naturalism, academicism, romanticism, impressionism, realism, direction, aesthetics, artistic position, antiquity, new turn, advanced social sentiments, national culture, national literature, Barbizon school, spatial perspective, plastic anatomy.

INTRODUCTION

Realistic painting is a direction whose main goal is a truthful reflection of objective reality and signs of typicality.

N. Poussin "Dance to the Music of Time" 1636. (classicism)

Realism is an aesthetic and artistic position, according to which the task of art is to depict reality as accurately and objectively as possible. However, it is necessary to distinguish between the philosophical concepts of reality and reality and, accordingly, the concepts of realism and naturalism in art.

In the development of fine arts, mainly painting, realism as a creative direction rejected and destroyed the leading role of classicism, romanticism and academicism.

The word classicism comes from the Latin language and is an “exemplary” artistic movement in European art of the 17 th and 18 th centuries, focused on the ideals of the classics of ancient antiquity. An example of this is Nicolas Poussin’s work entitled “A Dance to the Music of

Francis Cotes. Portrait of a Woman, 1768. (academicism)

A. Kuindzhi. «Oaks» 1905. (romanticism)

Time,” which he worked on in 1636. Academicism is a trend in European art that developed in art academies of the 16 th-19 th centuries and is based on a dogmatic adherence to the external aspects of classical art. Academicism had a decisive influence on the systematization of art education and the strengthening of the classical tradition, which he considered a system of “eternal” laws and rules. We can see noteworthy aspects of academicism in Francis Coates’s Portrait of a Lady, which he worked on in 1768.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Romanticism is an ideological and artistic movement in European and American culture of the late 18th - first half of the 19 th centuries. It confirms the inner value of a person’s spiritual and creative life, shows characters full of strong passions, a state of mind and natural landscapes as healing. It has spread to various spheres of human activity. In the 18th century, everything that was strange, beautiful, and existed in books and not in reality was called romantic. At the beginning of the 19 th century,

E.Preyer. «Natureworth» 1873. (naturalism)

I.Shishkin. «Oaks» 1886. (realism)

G. Courbet «Rocks at Etretat »1869. (realism)

romanticism became a sign of a new movement that opposed classicism and academicism.

Naturalism in the broadest sense: this is the tendency to fully and completely accurately reflect all the details of the appearance of reality. This tendency has constantly manifested itself in the fine arts and from time to time was formed in certain historical directions, movements, schools, creative styles and methods of individual masters.

At the beginning of the 19 th century, realism began to take shape in the depths of romanticism. This new turn was associated with progressive social sentiments and the strengthening of the formation of nations, national cultures, interest in ethnic history and culture, primarily in national literature.

The appearance of the term “realism” in painting is usually associated with the work of the French artist Gustave Courbet (1819-1877), who opened a private exhibition in Paris in 1855 in the specially created “Pavilion of Realism,”

although earlier. Artists of the Barbizon school worked realistically (Theodore Rousseau, Jean-François Millet, Jules Breton). In the 70s of the 18th century, realism was divided into two main directions - naturalism in academic art and impressionism, whose representatives initially called themselves naturalists.

RESULTS

Realism is a work of art that is detailed and photographically accurate to an astonishing degree.

Impressionism - (comes from the French word "impression" - meaning impression) - the task of artists of this direction is to convey to the viewer through their emotions the impression of nature in the air. This movement originated in the 1860s, and in 1874 the first Impressionist exhibition was organized in Paris.

This exhibition featured works by French impressionist artists such as Claude Monet, Pierre Auguste Renoir, Edgar Degas, Edouard Manet, Alfred Sisley, Camille Pissarro. From the 1870s, the realist movement began to spread in Russia, where realistic painting developed to an

*K. Monet. «Self-portrait». 1886.
(impressionism)*

unprecedented level. A.K. Savrasov, I.K. Aivazovsky, I.E. Repin, V.I. Surikov, V.A. Serov, I.I. Levitan, I.I. Shishkin, K.P. A number of Russian artists, such as Bryullov and Hokoza, further enriched the art of realism with their works.

In the 1930s, the work of a number of Russian realist artists came to Uzbekistan, such as Pavel Benkov, Volkov (pseudonym Master Momin), U. Tansikboev, Ch. The impetus for the formation of representatives of the older generation was provided by such Uzbek artists as Akhmarov, R. Akhmedov, N. Abdullaev, S. Abdullaev, N. Koziboev. They serve as an important basis for the development of Uzbek realistic art.

DISCUSSION

The main task of realistic art in training artist-teachers at the level of the requirements of the time is to ensure that they rely on the principles of perspective

and the laws of plastic anatomy, which are the basis of realism, in a true depiction of existence. Without this, it is impossible to prepare the personnel in demand in the modern era. Because the foundations of realism play an important role in shaping the aesthetic consciousness and creative thinking potential of the future generation.

CONCLUSION

That is why practical classes provided for by the requirements of the state educational standard are intended to be carried out on the basis of the principles of realism, based on step-by-step rules.

REFERENCES

1. Виталий Манин. «ИВАН ШИШКИН». Издательство «Белый город». г. Москва. 2004 г. 44-48.
2. В. А. Кулаков. «КЛЮД МОНЕ». Издательство «Изобразительное искусство». г. Москва. 1989 г. 5-12.
3. TolipovN., AbdirasilovS., OripovaN. «RANGTASVIR» (2-qism). O‘quv qo‘llanma, Toshkent., 2003. TDPU –B. 5-19.
4. Yunusaliyev, M. T. (2023). AKVAREL TEXNIKASIDA RANGLAR LOYQALANSHNING OLDINI OLISH SHARTLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(7), 269-276.
5. Yunusaliyev, M. T. (2023). SUV-BO ‘YOQ TEXNIKASIDA AKVAREL VA GUASH MATERIALINING AHAMIYATI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(8), 353-361.
6. Yunusaliyev, M. (2023). THE VALUE OF WATERCOLOR AND GOUACHE MATERIAL IN THE TECHNIQUE OF WATER-BASED PAINT. *Science and innovation*, 2(C9), 5-10.
7. Yunusaliyev, M. (2023). CONDITIONS TO PREVENT COLOR POLLUTION IN WATERCOLOR TECHNIQUE. *Science and innovation*, 2(C7), 45-49.
8. Yunusaliyev, M. (2023). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF WATERCOLOR IN THE FORMATION OF PAINTING. *Science and innovation*, 2(C4), 80-87.
9. Madaminov, N. M., Yunusaliyev, M. T., & Mamurov, A. A. (2022). TASVIRIY SAN’ATDA RANGLAR GARMONIYASI (TSEBETOTERAPIYA) ORQALI INSONLARNI DAVOLASHNING O ‘ZIGA XOSLIGI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(12), 1265-1272.
10. Sohibov, R. (2023). RANGLARNING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI VA ULARNING AMALIY SAN’ATDA QO‘LLANILISHI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(7), 74-80.
11. Мадаминов, Н. М. (2022). ТАЪЛИМДА ИНФОРМАЦИОН ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ВА ТАЛАБАЛАРДА КАСБИЙ КЎНИКМАЛАРНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 200-203.
12. Мадаминов, Н. М. (2022). ТАЪЛИМ ЖАРАЁНИДА ТАСВИРИЙ САНЪАТНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ВА КОМПЬЮТЕР ГРАФИКАСИДАН КЕНГ ФОЙДАЛАНИШ ЕЧИМЛАРИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 46-50.
13. Sohibov, R. (2023). RANGLARNING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI VA ULARNING AMALIY SAN’ATDA QO‘LLANILISHI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(7), 74-80.
14. Mamirjonovich, M. N., Jumadillayevich, S. R., & Anvarovich, M. A. (2021). The Role Of Historical Monuments In The Development Of Central Asian Architecture. *The American Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 3(02), 1-5.
15. Sohibov, R. (2022). KOMPOZITSIYANING NAZARIY ASOSLARI. KOMPOZITSIYA HAQIDA UMUMIY TUSHUNCHALAR. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 256-259.

16. Jalilova, R. (2022). TASVIRIY SAN'ATDA QALAMTASVIR TEXNOLOGIYASINI O'QITISHNING DIDAKTIK PRINSIPLARI. *Science and innovation*, 1(C2), 45-47.